

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Immigration Policy and Precarious Migrant Labour in the UK

Policy Brief

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Introduction

The I-CLAIM project investigates the living and working conditions of migrant households with precarious legal status in Europe. In the UK, migrant irregularity is not simply the result of unauthorised entry or individual rule breaking. Rather, it is actively produced and reproduced through a policy environment that, over the past two decades, has expanded immigration enforcement into the everyday spaces of work, housing, public services, education and policing ([Piemontese & Sigona, 2024](#)).

UK immigration law and policy have created what I-CLAIM researchers describe as an “irregularity assemblage” ([Sigona & van Liempt, 2025](#)): a system in which legal rules, bureaucratic procedures, employers, digital infrastructures and public narratives converge to make migrants’ legal status increasingly precarious. In this system, policies do not simply restrict rights; they can also generate irregularity by design. Escalating visa costs, rigid sponsorship systems, and data-sharing across institutions all contribute to situations where migrants lose status or struggle to maintain lawful residence.

This policy architecture is reinforced by the way migration is framed in political and media debates. Our analysis of the Narrative Construction of Migrant Irregularity in the UK ([Piemontese, 2025](#)) shows that migration is increasingly discussed through a binary distinction between legality and illegality, with heavy reliance on imagery of “small boats”, numerical indicators, and moralised distinctions between “deserving” and “undeserving” migrants. These narratives shape public understanding of migration and help legitimise increasingly restrictive policies while narrowing the space for rights-based discussions.

Public perceptions are also shaped by limited and uneven knowledge about migration. Evidence from our survey on Public Understanding and Attitudes to Irregular Migration in the UK ([Lessard-Phillips & Sigona, 2025](#)) shows that many people misunderstand how irregular migration actually occurs, often assuming it results primarily from unauthorised border crossings rather than visa overstays, bureaucratic barriers, or employer-linked migration regimes.

Against this backdrop, the I-CLAIM project has conducted two in-depth studies of migrant work in the food delivery and domestic work sectors. These sectors illustrate how immigration policies interact with labour market structures to shape everyday working conditions. Research on irregularised migrant workers in the UK food delivery sector ([Sigona, Piemontese, Achi, & Soares Mendes, 2025](#)) shows how delivery riders operate at the intersection of algorithmic management and intensified immigration enforcement targeting “illegal working”. Meanwhile, research on irregularised migrants in domestic work ([Sigona, Piemontese, Soares Mendes, & Achi, 2025](#)) highlights how restrictive visa routes and sponsorship systems channel migrant workers into isolation, overwork and, in some cases, situations resembling forced labour.

These findings reveal a clear pattern: the UK policy environment does not merely fail to prevent exploitation — it can structurally enable it. By criminalising border crossings, restricting access to work and services, embedding immigration checks into everyday life, and denying safe reporting mechanisms, the current system traps many irregularised migrants in situations where exploitation becomes widespread and accountability difficult. Migrants are often punished for the very precarity that state policies help to produce.

This policy brief draws on key findings from I-CLAIM research in the UK, as well as insights from conversations with migrant activists, trade unions, legal practitioners and civil society organisations. It sets out a series of

recommendations for improving the living and working conditions of irregularised migrant workers and their families.

Migrants have long been central to the UK's workforce and labour movement. Today they make up around one fifth of the UK labour force ([Fernández-Reino & Brindle, 2025](#)). Yet the current migration system undermines their rights, autonomy and ability to build stable lives. The UK urgently needs a migration and labour framework that protects people rather than weaponising legal status, and that enables all workers — regardless of where they were born — to live and work with dignity and security ([JCWI, 2024](#)).

1. Main research findings

1.1. The UK's legal and policy infrastructure actively produces irregularity

Irregular migration in the UK is not simply an accidental outcome of unauthorised entry. Rather, it is often the predictable result of interacting regulatory frameworks across immigration, labour and welfare systems. The combination of the Hostile Environment, the post-Brexit Points-Based System (PBS), and administrative pathways into status loss, creates structural pressures that push migrants into precarious or unlawful forms of residence.

Several mechanisms are particularly significant.

First, Hostile Environment policies have extended immigration enforcement into everyday life by delegating immigration checks to employers, landlords, banks, universities, local authorities and healthcare providers. This dispersal of enforcement increases the risk that bureaucratic errors, delays or misunderstandings can trigger loss of status and exclusion from services.

Second, the absence of safe reporting mechanisms means that migrants who experience labour exploitation, wage theft or violent crime often avoid contacting authorities for fear of immigration enforcement. This undermines labour inspections, weakens protections against modern slavery and trafficking, and ultimately compromises public safety.

Third, high visa costs, the Immigration Health Surcharge and restrictive sponsorship rules make it financially difficult for many low-paid migrants to maintain lawful status. Workers who entered the UK legally may fall into irregularity because they cannot afford renewal costs, lose their job, or become trapped in abusive employment relationships tied to sponsorship.

Fourth, post-Brexit changes have created new risks of irregularisation for EU citizens who were unable to successfully apply to the EU Settlement Scheme or to demonstrate continuous residence. This group remains largely invisible in public debates about irregular migration.

Finally, asylum reforms increasingly link asylum to “illegality”, leaving people in prolonged limbo and at risk of removal with limited rights of appeal.

1.2. Dominant public narratives construct irregularity through borders, criminalisation, and deservingness

Public and political debates play a central role in shaping migration policy. Our analysis of media, political and civil society narratives shows that irregular migration in the UK is frequently framed through a narrow discourse centred on border control and moral judgements about deservingness.

Across the political spectrum and media landscape, coverage disproportionately focuses on small boat crossings and enforcement measures, while the structural drivers of irregularity — such as visa overstays, bureaucratic barriers or employer-linked status loss — receive much less attention. This framing reinforces the perception that irregular migration is primarily a matter of border security.

Within this discourse, the figure of the “illegal migrant” functions as a moral counterpoint to the “deserving migrant”. Political narratives frequently contrast skilled workers, key workers or “legal migrants” with irregular migrants portrayed as burdens or threats. This moral distinction helps legitimise restrictive policies and normalises the withdrawal of rights.

Media portrayals also reproduce gendered and racialised stereotypes. Irregular migrant men are often depicted as threatening or criminal, while women are portrayed primarily as victims of sexual violence or as mothers. Such portrayals reduce complex experiences to simplified archetypes and obscure the structural conditions shaping migration and labour markets.

Civil society organisations often challenge these narratives by highlighting exploitation and structural drivers of irregularity. However, counter-narratives frequently rely on arguments about migrants’ economic contribution or humanitarian deservingness. While politically pragmatic, these strategies can unintentionally reproduce the same deservingness framework that underpins restrictive policies.

Overall, the narrative environment narrows the range of politically acceptable policy responses and makes rights-based reforms more difficult to advance.

1.3. Public perceptions of irregular migration are marked by knowledge gaps, racialised preferences, and ambivalent pragmatism

Survey evidence from 1,147 UK adults shows that public understanding of irregular migration is fragmented, uneven and strongly shaped by dominant political and media narratives.

A majority of respondents significantly overestimated the number of irregular migrants living in the UK. Many assumed that irregular migration primarily results from unauthorised border crossings rather than administrative pathways such as visa overstays or sponsorship breakdowns.

Attitudes were strongly influenced by age, political affiliation and ideology. Older respondents and voters aligned with Conservative or Reform parties were significantly more likely to perceive irregular migration as a major threat and to associate asylum seekers with illegality.

The survey also revealed racialised preferences in employment scenarios. When respondents were asked whether they would hire an irregular migrant care worker, factors such as longer residence in the UK, family

ties and positive references increased acceptance. However, candidates from Nigeria and Bangladesh were consistently less preferred than candidates from Moldova, revealing how migration governance intersects with racialised hierarchies in labour markets.

Finally, respondents' attitudes varied depending on social context. While most people expressed little concern about encountering irregular migrants in public settings such as shops or public transport, discomfort increased sharply when imagining irregular migrants working inside their homes. This finding highlights how private domestic spaces remain symbolically sensitive sites in debates about migrant labour.

1.4. In domestic work and domiciliary care, immigration status directly enables exploitation and housing control mechanisms

Research on migrant domestic workers and domiciliary care workers demonstrates how immigration policies interact with labour market conditions to produce exploitation.

Employer sponsorship systems create strong dependency relationships. Workers on Skilled Worker or Health and Care Worker visas often cannot change employer without restarting an expensive and complex visa process. Employers may therefore use the threat of withdrawing sponsorship to enforce compliance.

Many workers also incur high recruitment debts, ranging from £6,000 to £24,000, to secure employment in the UK. These debts can trap workers in abusive employment relationships and create conditions resembling debt bondage.

Housing arrangements frequently reinforce this dependency. Many live-in workers experience dual employer–landlord relationships, where eviction may simultaneously mean job loss and visa breach. Some workers are required to pay rent despite service occupancy arrangements, while others are incorrectly charged council tax.

Workers interviewed for the study described extremely long working hours, withheld wages, confiscated passports and restrictions on movement. In the absence of effective labour inspection in private homes, informal support networks — including churches, community groups and WhatsApp networks — often become the primary source of support.

1.5. In the food delivery sector, algorithmic management and immigration enforcement converge to produce extreme precarity

The food delivery sector illustrates how digital labour platforms and immigration enforcement increasingly intersect to shape migrant workers' livelihoods.

Participants in the study included undocumented migrants, asylum seekers, overstayers, EU citizens with pre-settled status and dependants on various visa routes. Despite differences in legal status, they described a shared experience of uncertainty, surveillance and economic coercion.

Platform regulation introduced in 2025 — including biometric identity checks, device restrictions and stricter account verification — has embedded immigration control within the architecture of platform work. Riders

frequently described platform algorithms as functioning “like a border guard”, determining who can access work and when.

These technological controls have also disrupted informal survival strategies. In the past, account sharing or renting allowed individuals without work authorisation to earn income. New biometric verification systems have largely dismantled these arrangements, pushing many irregularised migrants out of the sector and increasing the cost of rented accounts for those who remain.

The consequences extend beyond the workplace. Riders described working 10–12 hour days in physically demanding conditions while facing constant fear of immigration raids. This combination of immigration enforcement, platform surveillance and economic precarity has produced what stakeholders described as a hyper-visible but highly disposable workforce, disproportionately composed of racialised migrant workers.

2. Methodology

This policy brief draws on research conducted in the UK as part of the I-CLAIM project. The research combines multiple sources of evidence to examine how migrant irregularity is produced and experienced across policy frameworks, public narratives and labour markets.

The analysis integrates four main strands of research.

First, a policy analysis examined legislative and regulatory developments shaping migrant irregularity in the UK between 2005 and 2025, focusing on the interaction between immigration, labour and welfare policies. This analysis was complemented by 11 interviews with key stakeholders, including representatives from trade unions, migrant rights organisations and legal practitioners.

Second, a narrative analysis examined how irregular migration is framed in political, media and civil society discourse. The dataset included 6,816 texts published between 2019 and 2023, including newspaper articles, parliamentary debates, ministerial speeches, party manifestos and third-sector publications.

Third, public attitudes towards irregular migration were analysed using a nationally representative YouGov survey conducted in February 2025 with 1,147 UK adults.

Finally, the research examined the lived experiences of migrant workers in two labour market sectors where irregularised workers are particularly present: food delivery and domestic work. This component draws on 33 in-depth interviews conducted in Birmingham and the West Midlands between January and May 2025, alongside ethnographic observations and informal conversations with workers and community organisations.

Stakeholder engagement was embedded throughout the research through a dedicated UK Stakeholder Group, which met three times between 2023 and 2025 and helped inform the interpretation of findings and the development of policy recommendations.

3. Policy recommendations

All workers need decent pay, safe conditions, protections and the means to change jobs and get support if they are exploited, no matter what papers they hold. All workers need protection from exploitative employers and workplaces, as well as from immigration raids on workplaces and homes. Migrants' rights must be understood as workers' rights, because securing better protections for migrant workers will improve wages and conditions for all workers. The evidence presented in this brief shows how immigration policies, labour market structures and public narratives interact to shape migrants' exposure to exploitation. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated action across national and local levels of governance, including local authorities and local representatives, central government and political representatives, civil society, trade unions and migrant workers.

3.1. Strengthen safe reporting mechanisms and firewall protections for all workers, irrespective of their immigration status

Migrant workers must be able to report labour exploitation, wage theft, unsafe working conditions, abuse, and violence without fear that doing so will trigger immigration enforcement. Current data-sharing arrangements between labour enforcement bodies, police forces, local authorities, and immigration enforcement discourage and prevent many migrants from seeking help or reporting exploitation, undermining both labour protections and public safety.

UK Government and Parliament

- End the criminalisation of irregular working and related enforcement measures that increase vulnerability to exploitation.
- End data-sharing between the Home Office, police forces, and labour enforcement bodies, including the future Fair Work Agency.
- Establish clearer separation between labour standards enforcement and immigration control.
- Introduce stronger whistleblower protections for migrant workers reporting exploitation, trafficking, or abuse.

Local Authorities and Public Bodies

- Ensure local services can be accessed safely and without fear of immigration enforcement.
- Ensure local inspection and regulatory teams do not share information with immigration enforcement authorities.
- End joint inspections involving local authorities and immigration enforcement.
- Support community know-your-rights and anti-raid initiatives.
- Trade Unions and Civil Society
- Expand outreach and organising among migrant workers in precarious situations.
- Strengthen referral pathways between unions, migrant organisations, legal advisers, and labour inspectors.

Employers and Labour Platforms

- Ensure grievance and whistleblowing procedures are accessible to all workers irrespective of immigration status.

- End use of immigration status or threats of immigration enforcement as tools of workplace discipline.

3.2. Reduce dependency and exploitation created by employer-tied visa systems

Research conducted through the I-CLAIM project shows that employer-tied visa systems can create strong dependency relationships that increase workers' vulnerability to exploitation, debt, and abuse. Workers on sponsorship-based visas often face significant barriers to changing employers, while high recruitment costs and restrictive immigration rules can trap migrants in precarious and exploitative situations.

UK Government and Parliament

- End the system of work sponsorship and ensure that all work visas come with the option to safely change jobs.
- Strengthen oversight of recruitment agencies and enforce prohibitions on illegal recruitment fees and debt-financed migration.
- Provide clear and more accessible pathways to residence and settlement for migrant workers and their families.
- Ensure clear routes to regularisation for all, drawing on initiatives introduced elsewhere in Europe, including Spain's 2026 regularisation programme.

Employers and Recruitment Agencies

- Ensure transparent recruitment processes and prohibit the charging of unlawful recruitment fees.
- Provide workers with clear information about their employment rights, visa conditions, and routes to support.
- Trade Unions and Civil Society
- Support sponsored workers facing exploitation, unfair dismissal, or sponsorship withdrawal.
- Expand legal advice and advocacy for migrant workers trapped in abusive sponsorship arrangements.

3.3. Address administrative pathways into irregular status

Many migrants enter the UK through established or official channels but later fall into irregular status due to restrictive visa conditions, high renewal costs, administrative delays, or sudden changes in employment and family circumstances. The current system too often produces irregularity through bureaucratic barriers, increasing vulnerability to exploitation, homelessness, and destitution.

UK Government and Parliament

- Reduce the cumulative costs associated with visa renewals, extensions, and the Immigration Health Surcharge, particularly for low-paid workers and families.
- Introduce greater flexibility in renewal deadlines and status transitions to prevent avoidable losses of lawful status.
- Simplify administrative procedures for workers changing employers or visa categories.

- End No Recourse to Public Funds (NRPF) restrictions, given their role in increasing destitution and exploitation.
- Introduce clear regularisation pathways for all residents.

Local Authorities and Public Bodies

- Ensure that migrants experiencing administrative barriers or status insecurity can access accurate information, legal advice, and referral services.
- Work with community organisations to reduce risks of homelessness, destitution, and social exclusion among people with insecure immigration status.
- Civil Society and Legal Support Organisations
- Expand access to independent immigration advice and support for migrants at risk of falling into irregular status due to administrative barriers or changes in personal circumstances.
- Continue monitoring and documenting the impacts of restrictive immigration rules on long-term integration and labour market participation.

3.4. Strengthen labour protections in high-risk sectors

Research conducted through the I-CLAIM project highlights widespread exploitation in sectors such as domestic work, domiciliary care, and platform-based delivery services, where weak oversight, subcontracting, and employer dependency create conditions for abuse. Immigration status and insecure work arrangements are routinely used to discipline workers, suppress complaints, and normalise poor working conditions.

UK Government and Regulators

- Strengthen labour inspection and enforcement in sectors where exploitation is widespread, including domestic work, care work, and platform-based delivery services.
- Ensure that labour protections apply to all workers irrespective of immigration status.
- Introduce stronger regulation of subcontracting chains, recruitment agencies, and platform-based labour practices linked to exploitation and wage theft.
- Require digital labour platforms to provide transparent procedures for contesting account suspensions, deactivations, and algorithmic management decisions.
- Ensure any engagement with immigration enforcement in order not to undermine labour inspections or discourage workers from reporting abuse.

Local Authorities and Public Bodies

- Ensure that public procurement and contracting do not contribute to exploitative labour practices or abusive subcontracting chains.
- Terminate contracts with suppliers and providers found to be responsible for serious labour exploitation or abuse.

Employers and Labour Platforms

- End the use of opaque algorithmic systems, sponsorship dependency, and immigration status as mechanisms of labour discipline and control.
- Ensure safe working conditions, fair pay, and accessible grievance procedures for all workers.

- Trade Unions and Civil Society
- Expand organising, legal support, and outreach among migrant workers in highly precarious sectors.
- Develop community-based and multilingual strategies to support workers excluded from formal labour protections and union representation.

3.5. Promote evidence-based and anti-racist public debate on migration

Public debate on irregular migration is often shaped by misinformation, racialised narratives, and the conflation of migration with criminality and insecurity. The I-CLAIM research shows that public understanding of irregular migration is partial and uneven, with widespread overestimation of the number of irregular migrants and limited awareness of the administrative and policy processes that produce irregularity.

Political and media narratives that distinguish between “deserving” and “undeserving” migrants contribute to the normalisation of exclusionary policies and hostile public attitudes, while obscuring migrants’ contributions to society and the economy.

UK Government, Political Representatives, and Public Institutions

- Promote more accurate and transparent public communication on migration pathways, labour market participation, and the drivers of irregular status.
- Avoid rhetoric that criminalises migrants or conflates irregular migration with insecurity and criminality.
- Recognise and address the racialised impacts of immigration enforcement and public discourse.

Media Organisations and Regulators

- Challenge misleading and sensationalist representations of irregular migration.
- Avoid framing migrants primarily through the language of illegality, invasion, or crisis.
- Ensure greater representation of migrant voices and experiences in public debate.

Local Authorities, Trade Unions, and Civil Society

- Publicly challenge anti-migrant racism, misinformation, and narratives that scapegoat migrants for broader social and economic problems.
- Support public engagement initiatives that promote informed discussion of migration, labour rights, and social inclusion.
- Ensure that migrant workers and migrant-led organisations are meaningfully involved in policy discussions and public debate.

3.6. Strengthen local support and access to essential services

Local authorities and frontline services play a critical role in reducing vulnerability to exploitation, destitution, and social exclusion among migrants with precarious or irregular immigration status.

Access to healthcare, housing support, legal advice, language provision, and community services should not be undermined by fear of immigration enforcement or restrictive eligibility rules.

Local Authorities and Public Services

- Ensure that local services, including healthcare, housing support, ESOL provision, mental health services, and community advice, are accessible to all residents wherever permissible, irrespective of immigration status.
- Ensure that frontline staff are clearly informed about the ways in which they can provide alternative support or signpost people who are unable to access some forms of support due to their status
- Work with community organisations and migrant support groups to reduce risks of homelessness, destitution, and labour exploitation.
- Provide targeted support for people affected by No Recourse to Public Funds (NRPF) restrictions and partner with organisations specialising in NRPF support.

UK Government

- End NRPF restrictions and right-to-rent measures, that increase risks of homelessness, exclusion, and destitution among migrants with insecure status.
- Ensure that access to essential services and basic protections is not conditional on immigration status.

Civil Society, Community Organisations, and Trade Unions

- Expand outreach, legal advice, and welfare support for migrants facing insecure housing, poverty, or exclusion from public services.
- Strengthen partnerships between local services, migrant-led organisations, and trade unions to improve access to support and reduce isolation.

4. References

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